

Factors Related to Men Participation in the Use of Contraception in UPTD Puskesmas Tanjung Agung West Baturaja Subdistrict OKU District in 2019

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Abstract— Background: The low participation of men in family planning and reproductive health is basically inseparable from the operation of the family planning program that has been implemented so far that women are targeted. Likewise, the problem of providing contraceptives is almost all for women, so that the mindset of the community has a dominant perception, namely women who are pregnant and giving birth, so women must use contraception. **Objective:** To find out factors related to male participation in contraceptive use in UPTD Puskesmas Tanjung Agung, West Baturaja Sub District, OKU District in 2019. **Method:** This research uses analytic method with cross sectional approach. The population in this study were all of the Fertile Age Couples in UPTD Puskesmas Tanjung Agung, West Baturaja Subdistrict, OKU District in the May-June 2019 period, amounting to 97. Data analysis used univariate analysis and bivariate analysis using distribution tables and Chi-square statistical tests, with confidence level 95%. **Results:** In the bivariate analysis there was a relationship between male knowledge and male participation in contraceptive use with a p value of 0.021. There was a relationship between wife support and male participation in contraceptive use with a p value of 0.031. There is a relationship between the role of health workers with male participation in contraceptive use with a p value of 0.004. **Conclusion:** There is a relationship between men's knowledge, wife's support, the role of health workers with male participation in contraceptive use.

Keywords— Wife support, knowledge, the role of health workers, male participation in contraceptive use.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to WHO (World Health Organization) family planning is an action that helps married couples avoid unwanted pregnancies, get births that are very desirable, set intervals between pregnancies, control the time of birth in relation to the age of husband and wife and determine the number of children in family (Kursani, 2016).

Respect for reproductive rights in national family planning programs is carried out by campaigning for the role of decision making to use contraceptive methods in a balanced manner including efforts to increase male participation. Men's participation in family planning programs is very important because men are partners in reproduction, so husband and wife need to share responsibilities and roles equally (Yudi et al, 2015).

Talking about male participation indicators is quite interesting and needs to be studied further. Why do male contraception participants with the same contraception namely condoms and vasectomy in this country are higher, such as in Malaysia it is almost 16 percent, Japan 80 percent, America 35 percent and Iran 13 percent, as well as Bangladesh 13.9 percent. Men's participation is important in family planning and reproductive health because men are partners in reproduction and sex, are socially and economically responsible, and men are significantly involved in fertility and they have an important role in deciding the contraception to be used or used by his wife (Musyafaah), 2015).

The low participation of men in family planning and reproductive health is basically inseparable from the operation of the family planning program that has been implemented so far that it targets women. Likewise, the problem of providing contraceptives is almost all for women, so that the mindset of the community has a dominant perception, namely women who are pregnant and giving birth, so women must use contraception. Therefore, since 2000 the government has firmly made various efforts to increase men's participation in family planning and reproductive health through established policies (BKKBN, 2017).

The increase and expansion of family planning services is one of the efforts to reduce the morbidity and mortality rate of mothers so high. Increasing male participation in family planning, especially vasectomy, is one of the targets to be achieved by the family planning program in the long term (Wiyatmi, 2016).

Considering that most of the family decision-making is still dominated by husbands, the indicator of male participation according to BKKBN is not only as a KB participant but also supports the wife in using contraception, family planning service providers (motivators, promoters) and planning the number of children with spouses.

Based on the results of data in Air Gading Village in 2017 there were 204 active KB participants and 177 IDP contraception participants, 15 IUD implants as many as 11 MOW as many as 1, MOP as many as 0 people and 60 condoms. And in 2018 there were 221 active birth control participants and 197 injection contraception participants, 13

IUD implants, 9 MOW implants as many as 1, 1 MOP and 60 condoms, (Data of Desa Air Gading Puskesmas Tanjung Agung, 2019).

The low use of contraception among men is exacerbated by the impression so far that the family planning program is only intended for women, so men are more likely to be passive. This is also evident from the tendency of women workers as officers and promoters for the success of the family planning program, even though the practice of family planning is a family problem, where the family problem is a social problem which means it is also a problem of men and women (Darozatun, 2015).

II. METHOD

This type of research used in this study is an analytical survey with a cross-sectional approach which is a study in which the independent variables (knowledge, wife support, the role of health workers) and the dependent variable (male participation in contraceptive use) are collected at the same time. The population in this study were all participants of the Aktive KB in Air Gading Village, UPTD Puskesmas Tanjung Agung Work Area, West Baturaja Sub District, OKU District, amounting to 97 people. The sample is a portion of the total population taken using accidental sampling technique, amounting to 97 people. This research was conducted at the UPTD of Tanjung Agung Health Center, West Baturaja Sub District, OKU District.

III. RESULTS

1. Relationship between mother's age and the choice of using contraception

TABLE 1. Relationship between mother's age and the selection of contraceptive use in Air Gading Village Work Area UPTD Puskesmas Tanjung Agung, West Baturaja Sub District, OKU District in 2019.

No	Age	The choice of contraceptive use				Σ	%	P value
		To Wear		Do not use				
		F	%	F	%			
1.	Low	16	37,2	27	62,8	43	100	0,021
2.	High	8	14,8	46	85,2	54	100	
Total		24	24,7	73	75,3	97	100	

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on table 1, it can be seen that men who participated in contraceptive use among respondents with high knowledge are 16 respondents (37.2%) greater than respondents with low knowledge, namely as many as 8 respondents (14.8%). Chi square statistical test results obtained p value = 0.021, this means that there is a significant relationship between male knowledge and participation in contraceptive use.

2. The relationship of knowledge with the choice of contraceptive use

TABLE 2. Relationship of knowledge with the selection of contraceptive use in Air Gading Village Work Area UPTD Puskesmas Tanjung Agung, West Baturaja Sub District OKU District in 2019.

No	Knowledge	Selection of Contraception Use				Σ	%	P value
		To Wear		Do not use				
		f	%	f	%			
1.	Good	12	63,2	7	36,8	19	100	0,028
2.	Bad	5	23,8	16	76,2	21	100	
Total		17	42,5	23	57,5	40	100	

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on table 2 it can be seen that respondents who use contraception on respondents with good knowledge that is as many as 12 respondents (63.2%) is greater than respondents with bad knowledge that is as much as 5 respondents (23.8%). Chi square statistical test results obtained p value = 0.028, this means that there is a significant relationship between knowledge and the choice of contraceptive use.

3. Relationship of partner support with the choice of contraceptive use

TABLE 3. Relationship of partner support with the selection of contraceptive use in Air Gading Village Work Area UPTD Puskesmas Tanjung Agung, West Baturaja Sub District OKU District in 2019.

No	Partner Support	Selection of Contraception Use				Σ	%	P value
		To Wear		Do not use				
		f	%	f	%			
1.	Does not support	10	66,7	5	33,3	15	100	0,039
2.	Support	7	28,0	18	72,0	25	100	
Total		17	42,5	23	57,5	40	100	

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on table 3, it can be seen that respondents who use contraception in couples who are not supportive as many as 10 respondents (66.7%) are greater than respondents with supportive partners as many as 7 respondents (28.0%). Chi square statistical test results obtained p value = 0.0039 this means there is a significant relationship between partner support with the choice of contraceptive use.

IV. DISCUSSION

1. Relationship of male knowledge with male participation in contraceptive use

In this study the male knowledge variable is categorized into 2 namely high knowledge and low knowledge. From the results of the Bivariate analysis it can be seen that the men participating in contraceptive use in respondents with high knowledge are 16 respondents (37.2%) greater than respondents with low knowledge which is as many as 8 respondents (14.8%).

Chi square statistical test results obtained p value = 0.021, this means that there is a significant relationship between male knowledge and participation in contraceptive use. So the hypothesis that there is a meaningful relationship between men's knowledge and men's participation in contraceptive use is proven.

The results of this study are in line with Elmia and Umi's research showing there is a relationship between knowledge, and men's participation in family planning.

The results of this study are also supported by a study conducted by Saptono (2018) entitled factors related to men's participation in family planning also showed a significant relationship between the level of knowledge of male fertile couples with low husband participation in family planning. The results showed that couples of childbearing age with low knowledge tend not to participate in family planning compared to men of fertile age couples who are well-informed

with the Chi Square test results obtained p value = 0.009 OR 9,341, meaning that there is a relationship between knowledge and men's participation in family planning

2. Relationship between wife's support and men's participation in contraceptive use

In this study wife support variables are categorized into 2 namely Yes and No. Based on a bivariate analysis that men who participated in contraceptive use among respondents with a supportive wife were 13 respondents (39.4%) greater than respondents with a non-supportive wife ie 11 respondents (17.2%). Chi square statistical test results obtained p value = 0.031, this means that there is a significant relationship between wife support with participation in contraceptive use. So the hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between wife support and participation in contraceptive use is proven.

The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Dorazatun and Anwar (2015) showing that there is a significant relationship between wife support for contraceptive use for male participation in families p value less than 0.05, OR value = 12,931, which means that men whose wives are supportive of contraceptive use has a greater chance of 12,931 compared to men whose wives do not support contraceptive use.

The results of this study are also supported by research conducted by Utami (2014). Wife's support for contraceptive use is a picture of a wife's positive attitude towards family planning, if a married couple has a positive attitude towards family planning then they are more likely to use contraception.

3. Relationship between the role of health workers and male participation in contraceptive use

In this study the role of health staff variables are categorized into 2 namely role and no role. that men who participate in contraceptive use in respondents with health workers have a role that is 18 respondents (39.1%) is greater than respondents with health workers do not play a role ie as many as 6 respondents (11.8%).

Chi square statistical test results obtained p value = 0.004, this means that there is a significant relationship between the role of health workers with participation in contraceptive use. Then the hypothesis that there is a meaningful relationship between the role of health workers with participation in contraceptive use.

The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Masro (2016) the results of statistical tests using the Chi square test, stated a significant relationship between the role of health workers with the behavior of male KB acceptors ($p = 0,000$, $p < 0.05$).

According to Masro (2016) the role of health workers supports EFA behavior to participate and become a KB acceptor. Male family planning acceptors state that health workers who provide complete information about family planning services either choose the type of family planning method as well as the side effects of the family planning

method. In addition to good communication about family planning information provided by health workers to respondents, the role of these officers is also supported by the availability of competent health workers in health services.

V. CONCLUSION

From the results of research that has been carried out in the working area of the UPTD Puskesmas Tanjung Agung, West Baturaja Sub District, OKU District in 2019, the factors related to male participation in contraceptive use can be concluded as follows:

1. There is a relationship between men's knowledge and male participation in contraceptive use at the UPTD Puskesmas Tanjung Agung, West Baturaja Sub District, OKU District in 2019 with a P -value of 0.021.
2. There is a relationship between wife support and male participation in contraceptive use in UPTD Puskesmas Tanjung Agung, West Baturaja Sub District, OKU District in 2019 with a P -value of 0.031.
3. There is a relationship between the role of health workers and male participation in contraceptive use in UPTD Puskesmas Tanjung Agung, West Baturaja Sub District, OKU District in 2019 with a P -value of 0.004.

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